

SupportingInformationFile S1

Mathematica code for: Remodeling and the Evolution of Sexual Autonomy by Mate Choice

Samuel S. Snow^{1,2*} and Richard O. Prum²

*Corresponding author: samuel.s.snow@gmail.com

¹Université Toulouse 1 Capitole and Institute for Advanced Studies in Toulouse (IAST), Toulouse, France

²Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, Yale University, New Haven, Connecticut, 06511

This code builds the model equations and performs a numerical projection of the three-locus population-genetic model presented in the main text.

See Table 1 for definitions of alleles and key parameters.

*Note on parametrization: in the main text and Appendices S1–S3, we refer to the mutation parameter as "u" to avoid confusion with the subscript m used to denote male genotype frequencies. In the code below, the mutation parameter is denoted "m" and has been left as such to avoid the introduction of errors.

```
ClearAll[st, sb, at, c,  $\gamma$ , m, init, T1B1R1, T2B1R1, T1B2R1, T2B2R1, T1B1R2, T2B1R2, T1B2R2, T2B2R2, genotypes, r, msel, fsel, Output, u, ab, z1, z2, zb, T2, B2, R2, DTB, DTR, DBR, DTBR, Mating, s, mgenotypes, T21, B21, R21, DTB1, DTR1, DBR1, DTBR1,  $\Delta$ T2,  $\Delta$ B2,  $\Delta$ R2,  $\Delta$ DTB,  $\Delta$ DTR,  $\Delta$ DBR,  $\Delta$ DTBR, perturb, sr, materec, RecTable, MaskProb, ZygoteGenotypes, prob, zyg1, zyg2, zygoteProb, loop];
```

```
(*three-locus popgen simulation of  
Remodeling without direct costs to coercive mating*)
```

```
(*this model uses a probabilistic formulation for how  
females visit and mate at male territories. Females may either  
visit territories randomly or choose territories based on
```

the kind of remodeling trait (bower) they see. Once there, the male may either coerce them into mating there without the opportunity to evaluate their display, or the female may choose the mate with that male (given that he has not already coerced her) by some factor related to his attractiveness.*)

(*There is a locus for male display trait T2/T1, remodeling trait (protective bower) B2/B1, and female preference for the type of Remodeling trait (bower), R2/R1. We make two underlying assumptions in this model: 1) that all males will coerce if they have the opportunity, and 2) that all females have a preference for attractive T2 males*)

(*parameters:

(1-st) is the fraction by which males having the T2 allele survive relative to Males having the T1 allele. (1-sb) is the fraction by which males having the B2 allele survive relative to Males having the B1 allele.

(1-sr) is the fraction by which females having the R2 allele survive relative to females having the R1 allele.

(a+1) is the factor by which attractive T2 allele males have a relative advantage in mating success over T1 males.

(ab+1) is the factor by which

females with the R2 allele prefer to visit B2 bowers.

c is a number between 0 and 1 representing the rate of successful forced fertilization of a female, (or the likelihood of coercive attack) by a male without a protective bower (B2).

γ is a number between 0 and 1 representing the effectiveness of protective bowers at reducing a male's ability to coerce. If $\gamma=0$, then there is no effect, and if $\gamma=1$, then B2 males are unable to coerce, and females are free to choose the male based on his attractiveness once they are at his territory.

Lastly, we make an assumption of biased mutation at the T locus. This is meant as a proxy for a quantitative, multiallelic trait or some other process by which variation is maintained at the T locus, so that sexual selection is ongoing and we can explore the effects of sexual conflict over indirect effects in a simple population-genetic framework*)

(*the equilibrium conditions for a non-zero T2 in the absence of B and R are: $0 < st < 1$ and $0 < m < 1$ and $at > -1 + \frac{1+m}{(-1+m)(-1+st)}$ and $0 < c < \frac{at-2m-atm+st+atmst}{at+2m+atm+st-mst}$. See Appendix S2 and Supporting Information File S2 for derivation*)

(*use these conditions to determine appropriate parameter values*)

Manipulate $\left\{ \left[-1 + \frac{1+m}{(-1+m)(-1+st)} \right], \frac{at-2m-atm+(1+at)(-1+m)st}{at+2m+atm+st-mst} \right\}$,

$$\{\{m, 0.1\}, 0, 1\}, \{\{st, 0.1\}, 0, 1\}, \left\{\{at, 4\}, -1 + \frac{1+m}{(-1+m)(-1+st)}, 30\right\}\};$$

(*set parameters*)

```
at = 12;
ab = 12;
c = 0.5;
γ = 0.8;
st = 0.1;
sb = 0.1;
sr = 0.01;
```

(*recombination and mutation rate*)

```
rtb = 1/2;
rbr = 1/2;
m = 0.1;
```

(*The initial frequency for T2 is the equilibrium value for when B2 and R2 equal zero. This is where female preference for T2, mutation bias, and male coercion are in balance. See Appendix S2 and Supporting Information File S2 for derivation*)

$$Teq = \frac{1 - m + \frac{2(1+c+at)c}{st+c} \frac{m}{st+at(-1+c+st)}}{1+m};$$

(*In support of understanding the effect of the presence of R2/B2 on female sexual autonomy: we want to know the proportion of T2 males females get at equilibrium in the initial state as compared to when females hypothetically have full autonomy (when c=0). See Supporting Information File S2 for derivation. Throughout the model runs we calculate the proportion of matings with T2 males for R1 and R2 females to give insight into the process and to get a metric of autonomy at the end.*)

$$t2propeq = 1 - \frac{2 (1 + c + at c) m}{(-1 + m) (st + c st + at (-1 + c + st))};$$

(*same proportion but evaluated at c=0*)

$$t2propaut = 1 - \frac{2 m}{(-1 + m) (at (-1 + st) + st)};$$

(*initial genotype frequencies. We can look at how the introduction of the B2 abnd R2 alleles perturbs the system. *)

T2 = Teq;

B2 = 0.05;

R2 = 0.05;

DTB = 0;

DTR = 0;

DBR = 0;

DTBR = 0;

```
init = Solve[{T1B1R1 + T2B1R1 + T1B2R1 + T2B2R1 + T1B1R2 + T2B1R2 + T1B2R2 + T2B2R2 == 1,
  T2 == T2B1R1 + T2B2R1 + T2B1R2 + T2B2R2, B2 == T1B2R1 + T2B2R1 + T1B2R2 + T2B2R2,
  R2 == T1B1R2 + T2B1R2 + T1B2R2 + T2B2R2, DTB == (T2B2R1 + T2B2R2) - T2 * B2,
  DTR == (T2B1R2 + T2B2R2) - T2 * R2, DBR == (T1B2R2 + T2B2R2) - B2 * R2,
  DTBR == T2B2R2 - T2 * ((T1B2R2 + T2B2R2) - B2 * R2) -
    B2 * ((T2B1R2 + T2B2R2) - T2 * R2) - R2 * ((T2B2R1 + T2B2R2) - T2 * B2) - T2 * B2 * R2},
  {T1B1R1, T2B1R1, T1B2R1, T2B2R1, T1B1R2, T2B1R2, T1B2R2, T2B2R2}];
```

T1B1R1 = T1B1R1 /. init;

T2B1R1 = T2B1R1 /. init;

T1B2R1 = T1B2R1 /. init;

T2B2R1 = T2B2R1 /. init;

T1B1R2 = T1B1R2 /. init;

T2B1R2 = T2B1R2 /. init;

T1B2R2 = T1B2R2 /. init;

T2B2R2 = T2B2R2 /. init;

(*genotypes vector with initial allele frequencies and linkages*)

```
genotypes = Flatten[{T1B1R1, T2B1R1, T1B2R1, T2B2R1,
  T1B1R2, T2B1R2, T1B2R2, T2B2R2, T2, B2, R2, DTB, DTR, DBR, DTBR}];
```

(*set up the table of recombination probabilities that will yield the distribution of zygote genotypes resulting from each mated pairing*)

```

Nloci = 3;
Geno = 2^Nloci;
masklim = 2^(Nloci - 1);
recreate[1] = rtb;
recreate[2] = rbr;

(*Maskprob gives the probability for a particular pattern of
recombination (a mask), based on given values of recombination
rates between different loci ("recreate" vector above)*)

MaskProb = Function[{mask, Nloci},
  For[prob = 1; z = 1, z < Nloci, z++,
    If[BitGet[mask, z] == BitGet[mask, z - 1],
      prob *= (1 - recreate[z]),
      prob *= recreate[z]]];

(*generates the two zygote genotypes (zyg1 and zyg2)
from two parental genotypes (i and j) for a given mask.*)

ZygoteGenotypes = Function[{i, j, mask},
  For[zyg1 = 0; zyg2 = 0; k = 0, k < Nloci, k++,
    If[BitGet[mask, k] == 0,
      zyg1 = BitOr[zyg1, (BitAnd[i, (2^k)])];
      zyg2 = BitOr[zyg2, (BitAnd[j, (2^k)])];
      zyg1 = BitOr[zyg1, (BitAnd[j, (2^k)])];
      zyg2 = BitOr[zyg2, (BitAnd[i, (2^k)])]]];

(*Produce a 3-dimensional matrix with the cells representing
the probability of producing a zygote genotype (k) from parental
genotypes i (mother) and j (father). Multiplying this matrix with
the mating table that gives the proportions of different male-
female genotype mating combinations will give the
frequency of zygote genotypes in the new generation
(after summing across parental genotypes).*)

RecTable = Table[0, {i, Geno}, {j, Geno}, {k, Geno}];
For[i = 0, i < Geno, i++,
  For[j = 0, j < Geno, j++,
    For[mask = 0, mask < masklim, mask++,
      MaskProb[mask, Nloci];
      zygoteProb = (1/2) * prob;
      ZygoteGenotypes[i, j, mask];
      RecTable[[i + 1, j + 1, zyg1 + 1]] += zygoteProb;
      RecTable[[i + 1, j + 1, zyg2 + 1]] += zygoteProb;]]]

(*uncomment this line to view the recombination table*)
(*MatrixForm[RecTable]*)

```

```
Output = {{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18},
  Flatten[{genotypes, 0, 0}]}];
```

```
loop = 0;
```

```
(*Uncommenting the following two lines and the section indicated below will
add a random perturbation to the system when it reaches equilibrium the
first time and then continue the simulation until it settles on equilibrium
again. This was done in our numeric simulations through parameter space for
Figure 3 and Figure S2.1 to avoid slow convergence on local optima. Since
the system always returns to nearly identical equilibrium values
following perturbation for the parameter set used to produce Figure 2,
the perturbation was omitted in that case for aesthetic purposes*)
```

```
(*perturb=0;
(Label[start];*)
```

```
(*begin the generation loop. The model will iterate until the genotype
frequencies and linkages are constant to seven decimal places*)
```

```
While[
  SetAccuracy[Last[Output], 7] ≠ SetAccuracy[Output[[Length[Output] - 1]], 7],

  (*make a vector that will perform Natural Selection on males,
  affecting gene frequencies before mating.*)

  msel = Table[i, {i, 1, 8}];
  u = Total[genotypes[[{1, 5}]]] + (1 - st) * Total[genotypes[[{2, 6}]]] + (1 - sb) *
    Total[genotypes[[{3, 7}]]] + (1 - sb) * (1 - st) * Total[genotypes[[{4, 8}]]];
  msel[[{1, 5}]] = Table[genotypes[[i]] / u, {i, {1, 5}}];
  msel[[{2, 6}]] = Table[((1 - st) * genotypes[[i]]) / u, {i, {2, 6}}];
  msel[[{3, 7}]] = Table[((1 - sb) * genotypes[[i]]) / u, {i, {3, 7}}];
  msel[[{4, 8}]] = Table[((1 - sb) * (1 - st) * genotypes[[i]]) / u, {i, {4, 8}}];

  zb = Total[msel[[{1, 2, 5, 6}]]] + (ab + 1) * Total[msel[[{3, 4, 7, 8}]]];

  z1 = Total[msel[[{1, 5}]]] * (c + (1 - c) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
    Total[msel[[{2, 6}]]] * (c + (1 - c) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2))) +
    Total[msel[[{3, 7}]]] * (c * (1 - γ) + (1 - c * (1 - γ)) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
    Total[msel[[{4, 8}]]] * (c * (1 - γ) + (1 - c * (1 - γ)) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2)));

  z2 = (Total[msel[[{1, 5}]]] / zb) * (c + (1 - c) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
    (Total[msel[[{2, 6}]]] / zb) * (c + (1 - c) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2))) +
    Total[msel[[{3, 7}]]] * ((1 + ab) / zb) * (c * (1 - γ) + (1 - c * (1 - γ)) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
    Total[msel[[{4, 8}]]] * ((1 + ab) / zb) *
```

```

(c * (1 - γ) + (1 - c * (1 - γ)) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2)));

(*Selection on females resulting
from cost of the female bower preference, R2*)

fsel = Table[i, {i, 1, 8}];
v = Total[genotypes[[1 ;; 4]] + (1 - sr) * Total[genotypes[[5 ;; 8]]];
fsel[[1 ;; 4]] = Table[genotypes[[i]] / v, {i, 1, 4}];
fsel[[5 ;; 8]] = Table[((1 - sr) * genotypes[[i]]) / v, {i, 5, 8}];

(*mating probability matrix-what proportion of matings will
be from each pairing strictly based on genotype frequency,
female choice, coercion, and bower type.*)
(*note that the mating matrix in the code here
is the transpose of the arrangement presented in Table 2,
with female genotypes as the "rows" and male genotypes as the
"columns." This is purely organizational; they are exactly equivalent*)

Mating = Table[Table[i, {i, 1, 8}], {j, 1, 8}];

(*for mating with R1 females*)

(*T1B1 males*)
Mating[[1 ;; 4, {1, 5}]] =
Table[Table[ $\frac{fsel[[j]] \left( msel[[i]] \left( c + \frac{1-c}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z1}$ , {i, {1, 5}}], {j, 1, 4}];

(*T2B1 males*)
Mating[[1 ;; 4, {2, 6}]] =
Table[Table[ $\frac{fsel[[j]] \left( msel[[i]] \left( c + \frac{(1-c)(at+1)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z1}$ , {i, {2, 6}}], {j, 1, 4}];

(*T1B2 males*)
Mating[[1 ;; 4, {3, 7}]] =
Table[Table[ $\frac{fsel[[j]] \left( msel[[i]] \left( c(1-\gamma) + \frac{1-c(1-\gamma)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z1}$ , {i, {3, 7}}], {j, 1, 4}];

(*T2B2 males*)
Mating[[1 ;; 4, {4, 8}]] = Table[
Table[ $\frac{fsel[[j]] \left( msel[[i]] \left( c(1-\gamma) + \frac{(1-c(1-\gamma))(at+1)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z1}$ , {i, {4, 8}}], {j, 1, 4}];

(*for mating with R2 females*)

(*T1B1 males*)

```

```

Mating[5 ;; 8, {1, 5}] =
Table[Table[ $\frac{f_{sel}[j] \left( m_{sel}[i] \left( c + \frac{1-c}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z_b z_2}$ , {i, {1, 5}}], {j, 5, 8}];
(*T2B1 males*)
Mating[5 ;; 8, {2, 6}] =
Table[Table[ $\frac{f_{sel}[j] \left( m_{sel}[i] \left( c + \frac{(1-c)(at+1)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z_b z_2}$ , {i, {2, 6}}], {j, 5, 8}];
(*T1B2 males*)
Mating[5 ;; 8, {3, 7}] = Table[
Table[ $\frac{f_{sel}[j] \left( m_{sel}[i] (1+ab) \left( c(1-\gamma) + \frac{1-c(1-\gamma)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z_b z_2}$ , {i, {3, 7}}], {j, 5, 8}];
(*T2B2 males*)
Mating[5 ;; 8, {4, 8}] = Table[Table[
 $\frac{f_{sel}[j] \left( m_{sel}[i] (1+ab) \left( c(1-\gamma) + \frac{(1-c(1-\gamma))(at+1)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z_b z_2}$ , {i, {4, 8}}], {j, 5, 8}];

(*here we sample the mating frequencies
in order to calculate the proportion of T2 males the
different female genotypes are mating with each generation*)

r2prop = Total[Total[Mating[5 ;; 8, {2, 4, 6, 8}]]] /
(Total[Total[Mating[5 ;; 8, {2, 4, 6, 8}]]] +
Total[Total[Mating[5 ;; 8, {1, 3, 5, 7}]]]);

r1prop = Total[Total[Mating[1 ;; 4, {2, 4, 6, 8}]]] /
(Total[Total[Mating[1 ;; 4, {2, 4, 6, 8}]]] +
Total[Total[Mating[1 ;; 4, {1, 3, 5, 7}]]]);

(*proportion of T2 matings overall, before recombination and mutation*)

t2prop = Total[Total[Mating[1 ;; 8, {2, 4, 6, 8}]]];

(*Multiply the mating table by the recombination
matrix to get the contributions to each zygote genotype
weighted by the proportions of each mate pairing*)

materec = RecTable * Mating;

(*sum across each element of each 8-tuple for the mate pairings
across the new matrix to get the final genotype frequencies.*)
genotypes[1 ;; 8] =
Table[Simplify[Total[Flatten[materec[1 ;; 8, 1 ;; 8, i]]]], {i, 1, 8}];

```

(*once genotypes are assigned, some frequency from T2 alleles are shifted over to T1 alleles due to biased mutation*)

```
mgenotypes = {1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8};
mgenotypes[[{2, 4, 6, 8}]] = (1 - m) * genotypes[[{2, 4, 6, 8}]];
mgenotypes[[{1, 3, 5, 7}]] = m * genotypes[[{2, 4, 6, 8}]] + genotypes[[{1, 3, 5, 7}]];
```

```
T21 = Total[mgenotypes[[{2, 4, 6, 8}]]];
B21 = Total[mgenotypes[[{3, 4, 7, 8}]]];
R21 = Total[mgenotypes[[5 ;; 8]]];
DTB1 = Total[mgenotypes[[{4, 8}]]] - T21 * B21;
DTR1 = Total[mgenotypes[[{6, 8}]]] - T21 * R21;
DBR1 = Total[mgenotypes[[{7, 8}]]] - B21 * R21;
DTBR1 = mgenotypes[[8]] - T21 * DBR1 - B21 * DTR1 - R21 * DTB1 - T21 * B21 * R21;
```

```
genotypes[[1 ;; 8]] = mgenotypes[[1 ;; 8]];
genotypes[[9 ;; 15]] = Flatten[{ T21, B21, R21, DTB1, DTR1, DBR1, DTBR1}];
```

```
Output = Append[Output, Flatten[{genotypes, r2prop, r1prop, t2prop}]];
loop = loop + 1; If[loop > 1000000, Break[]];];
```

(*Uncomment following code to add the random perturbation*)

```
(*If[perturb==0,
  tempx1=Table[1,{i,8}];
  index=Flatten[Position[genotypes[[1;;8]],Max[genotypes[[1;;8]]]];
  (*Find the position number of the genotype
  in the genotypes vector that is largest*)
  tempx1[[index]] = genotypes[[index]]*0.9 (*take 99% of the genotype frequency
  for the genotype of interest, this will be the new value*);
  perttot1 = (genotypes[[index]]-tempx1[[index]]);
  (*the total frequency taken from the original genotype*)
  Clear[t1];eight=Table[i,{i,8}];
  randomset=Delete[eight,index];
  Do[t1[k] = RandomReal[], {k,randomset}];
  (*creates random real numbers
  between zero and one and indexes them as t1[1], t1[2],
  t1[3].. skipping over the focal genotype that has lost frequency*)
  sumrand1 = Sum[t1[k], {k,randomset}];
  (*the sum of the random numbers
  generated associated with each other genotype*)
  Do[tempx1[[k]] = genotypes[[k]] + t1[k]*perttot1/sumrand1, {k,randomset}];
  (*divides and normalizes the random
  number and then distributes it to the other genotypes,
  indexed in the temporary vector as tempx1[[2]], tempx1[[3]], etc. basically
  each genotype receives a random portion of the frequency taken*)
  Do[genotypes[[k]] = tempx1[[k]], {k,8}];
```

```

(*last line assigns the new randomly redistributed
  genotypes back to the genotype vector used in the model loop*)
genotypes=Flatten[genotypes];

perturb=1;

T21=Total[genotypes[[{2,4,6,8}]]];
B21=Total[genotypes[[{3,4,7,8}]]];
R21=Total[genotypes[[5;;8]]];
DTB1=Total[genotypes[[{4,8}]]]-T21*B21;
DTR1=Total[genotypes[[{6,8}]]]-T21*R21;
DBR1=Total[genotypes[[{7,8}]]]-B21*R21;
DTBR1=genotypes[[8]]-T21*DBR1-B21*DTR1-R21*DTB1-T21*B21*R21;

genotypes[[9;;15]]=Flatten[{ T21,B21,R21,DTB1,DTR1,DBR1,DTBR1}];

Output=Append[Output,Flatten[{genotypes,r2prop,r1prop,t2prop}]];

Goto[start];];);*)

```

(*make sure to do the plots in Mathematica 10 or higher*)

`In[]:= (*plot of the frequencies of T, B, and R,
all together on one graph. T is black, B is blue, R is red*)`

```
ListPlot[{{Output[[2 ;; Length[Output], 9]], Output[[2 ;; Length[Output], 10]],  
Output[[2 ;; Length[Output], 11]]}, PlotRange -> {0, 1.01}, Joined -> True,  
PlotStyle -> {{Thick, Black, Dashing[Small]}, {Thick, ColorData[1, 1]},  
{Thick, Dashing[{0.025, 0.01}], ColorData[1, 2]}},  
ImageSize -> 576, DataRange -> {0, Length[Output] - 2}, Frame -> True,  
PlotRangePadding -> {{0, 3}, {0, 0.01}}, FrameStyle ->  
{{{18, Black, FontFamily -> "Times"}, {18, Black, FontFamily -> "Times"}},  
{{18, Black, FontFamily -> "Times"}, {18, Black, FontFamily -> "Times"}},  
FrameLabel -> {Text[Style["Generation", FontFamily -> "Times", FontSize -> 22]],  
Text[Style["Allele Frequency", FontFamily -> "Times", FontSize -> 22]]},  
ImagePadding -> {{90, 20}, {55, 35}}, AspectRatio -> 1 / (GoldenRatio)]
```



```

In[ ]:= (*plot of the proportion of T2 males mated with by R2 and R1 females;
R1 is blue and R2 is orange,
T2 is green. The dotted line represents full autonomy*)
autonomy =
ListPlot[{Output[[3 ;; Length[Output], 17]], Output[[3 ;; Length[Output], 16]],
  Output[[3 ;; Length[Output], 18]], Table[t2propaut, {i, Length[Output] - 3}],
  Table[t2propeq, {i, Length[Output] - 3}]],
PlotRange -> {0.4, 1.01}, Frame -> True, FrameStyle ->
  {{{18, Black, FontFamily -> "Times"}}, {18, Black, FontFamily -> "Times"}},
  {{{18, Black, FontFamily -> "Times"}}, {18, Black, FontFamily -> "Times"}},
FrameLabel -> {Text[Style["Generation", FontFamily -> "Times", FontSize -> 22]],
  Pane[Text[Style[Row[{"Proportion Matings", " with ",
    Subscript["T", "2"], " Males"}], FontFamily -> "Times"]],
    {170, All}, Alignment -> Center]}, ImagePadding -> {{90, 20}, {60, 10}},
PlotRangePadding -> {{0, 3}, {0, 0}}, PlotStyle -> {{Thick, ColorData[97, 1]},
  {Thick, ColorData[97, 2]}, {Thick, Dashed, ColorData[97, 3]},
  {Black, Dotted, Thickness[0.002]}, {Black, Dotted, Thickness[0.002]}},
Joined -> True, DataRange -> {1, Length[Output] - 2}, ImageSize -> 576,
AspectRatio -> 1 / (2 * GoldenRatio),
PlotLegends -> Placed[LineLegend[{Row[Subscript["R", "1"], "♀"],
  Row[Subscript["R", "2"], "♀"], "overall"], LabelStyle ->
  {18, FontFamily -> "Times"}, LegendLayout -> "Row", {0.66, 0.15}]]

```


(*Plot of the frequencies of R2 (x axis) and B2 (y axis)

```
In[*]:= ListPlot[Table[{Output[[i, 11]], Output[[i, 10]]}, {i, 2, Length[Output]}],
  PlotRange -> Full, Joined -> True, AspectRatio -> 1]
```



```
In[*]:= (*plots of all two- and three-way linkages: *)
linklabels = {"DTB", "DTR", "DBR", "DTBR"};
Table[ListPlot[Output[[2 ;; Length[Output], i]],
  PlotRange -> {-0.02, 0.05}, Joined -> True, Filling -> Axis,
  PlotLabel -> linklabels[[i - 1]], ImageSize -> Medium], {i, 12, 15}]
```


